

DETERMINING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE VIRTUAL GRAMMAR ASSISTANT 'GRAMMARLY' ON IMPROVING WRITING SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on the effectiveness of a virtual grammar assistant in improving writing skills among students selected from a higher educational institution residing in Pampanga, Philippines. Forty senior high school students from Grades 11 to 12 were selected using the purposive sampling technique based on the results of the survey. The result of this study will be beneficial to students, teachers, school administrators, curriculum planners, and future researchers. The study employed a quantitative approach. To get the average or mean of all the data, divide the total number of figures by the total number of figures in the collection after obtaining the data set. The collected data was tallied, manually processed, and used on a computer to determine the exact outcome. Data were gathered, totaled, and examined. Students are strengthening their writing abilities, particularly with regard to following correct English grammar, which is an essential component of their education as they look for methods to improve their academic achievement. They provide students with an invaluable resource to improve their writing abilities, and virtual grammar is more helpful for the students. These assistants analyze and provide real-time feedback on grammar usage, sentence construction, and paragraph coherence. The study utilizes a descriptive research design to provide objective and measurable insights into the effectiveness of virtual grammar assistance in enhancing writing skills.

Keywords: *Virtual Grammar Assistant, Writing Skills, Senior High School, Language, Learning*

INTRODUCTION

In today's digital age, effective communication through writing is paramount. Whether in academic, professional, or personal contexts, the ability to convey ideas with clarity and precision is a valuable skill. However, many individuals struggle with grammar and writing conventions, hindering their ability to effectively communicate. The advent of virtual grammar assistants, powered by artificial intelligence, promises to be a transformative tool in addressing these challenges. As the internet is around the world, virtual grammar assistant is now prevalent to the students as they are benefited from this because it gives assistance to them on their writing activities, however despite how helpful this is, there is still a problem that needs to be tackled. In the middle of the growth of virtual grammar assistance, it shows that students are the most benefited users of all the users.

The use of technology in education, according to Gilakjani & Sabouri (2014), has changed teachers' perceptions of their ability to be innovative in the teaching-learning process. Technology can help teachers in EFL classes assist the teaching-learning process and boost students' interest in the material. Additionally, technology has made it possible for people to develop their language abilities, including English. Due to their access to a plethora of knowledge, students may utilize technology to influence their learning in ways that instructors cannot. Additionally, by using technology to look for language exercises, children may advance their language abilities. One of the linguistic abilities that technology may help with is writing.

Digital technologies are having a variety of effects on students' writing and are also proving to be useful instructional tools for middle and high school students who are beginning to write, according to a survey of 2,462 AP and National Writing Project (NWP) instructors. Teachers contend that digital technologies, including text messaging, social networking sites, and mobile phones, as well as the internet, foster kids' creative and personal expression. Moreover, they also contribute to increasing the potential audience for their written work and promoting more frequent writing compared to previous generations, across a range of different formats (Purcell et al. 2013).

The rise of virtual grammar assistants over the past decade, virtual grammar assistants have proliferated in various forms (Babina et.al 2023). These tools harness the power of AI and natural language processing to identify and rectify grammatical errors, spelling mistakes, and stylistic issues. Their availability in word processors, web browsers, and standalone applications has made them accessible to a wide audience. The convenience and ubiquity of these tools have led to increased interest in their potential impact on improving writing skills. Majority of the students worldwide have relied on different grammar assistant to enhance their writing skills and proficiency in communicating through written messages.

Effective writing means a lot in terms of communication. It elevates the connection between people across the globe through a wide series of connectivity. As specified by

Neikirk (2023), the importance of effective writing skills are fundamental to academic success, workplace success, and beyond, because being able to write well is essential for effectively and accurately communicating thoughts, ideas, and information. Clear and error-free writing not only conveys ideas persuasively but also enhances the credibility of the writer. In contrast, poor writing can lead to misunderstandings, miscommunication, and missed opportunities. The implications of subpar writing extend to academic grades, professional advancement, and even personal relationships. Therefore, finding effective ways to bolster these skills is of paramount importance. As per Aydin (2018) employing a grammar checker significantly enhanced the writing abilities of EFL students. This development was particularly noticeable for learners with poorer beginning writing proficiency. Accordingly, using a virtual grammar aid can help you improve the writing abilities of EFL students, particularly those with less developed writing skills. Furthermore, it's critical to employ virtual grammar combined with additional writing guidelines, including comments from professors or peers. By the means of that students can ensure that their work are more improved and enhanced.

As per Dolgunsöz (2018), IVR technology is being used to assist EFL learners in overcoming their challenges with their language skills, particularly their writing skills. Previous research indicated that the use of an immersion tool would enhance students' written performance. In today's era there a multivariate of sophisticated grammar checking tools which can aid students towards the development of their work. Another testament by Hee-Joo Im (2021) on their study have investigated the usage of online grammar checkers in English writing lessons and to recommend when they could be appropriate. 35 first-year students participated in the study, which was carried out at the University in Chungcheong-do. Pre and post-grammar tests, surveys, and learning journals were all gathered and examined as data sources. Following are the findings of this investigation. The online grammar checker was first discovered to be successful in English writing classes based on the outcomes of the English grammar test. The latter can detect kinds of typing errors that also help us. This will also help us to improve our readability, using an online grammar checker for any activity that we are going to do that can be improved. This intensify the claim that the use of virtual grammar assistant can help towards the improvement of students grammar and communication skills as found out by numerous researches across the globe.

Another claim by Huang et al. 2020, the use of Grammarly in writing lessons is a good strategy for helping EFL students improve their writing abilities and for assisting teachers in lightening their workload. As Grammarly is one of the famous virtual grammar assistants, every student uses this tool for their written outputs to make their grammar correct and less mistakes. In addition, this discusses how can grammarly help the students with their writing abilities and for the teacher to make their work easier. To sum up the discussion, Grammarly is a potential virtual grammar assistant to assist students and teachers with their writing activities or outputs. In accordance with Hyejin (2018), a grammar checker might be a helpful educational tool for writing low-level L2 learners using grammar. Advanced writing ability is a crucial need for pupils to demonstrate their understanding of contemporary concerns and clarity. It is also found that students who used an online grammar checker made significantly fewer grammatical errors in their

writing. Additionally, the latter found that students generally had positive perceptions of the grammar checker which strengthen the claim of the researchers in understanding the efficacy of the virtual grammar assistant Grammarly in enhancing the writing capacity of the students. Every student may benefit from using the virtual grammar assistant to improve their writing abilities and to identify and correct their grammatical and usage problems. Additionally, the use of a virtual grammar helper has a significant positive effect on all learners since it enables them to produce better writing as well as to fill in any writing gaps.

According to Maharani et al. (2023), writing is a difficult skill. It is supported by claims that writing is a difficult endeavor that requires a great lot of cognitive and language skills. Argues that the ability to recognize, comprehend, and explain an idea in a paragraph or essay is the most fundamental writing skill that pupils can have the capacity to perceive, analyze, and effectively communicate ideas in an organized format, such as a paragraph or essay, is critical for writers. This skill requires not just knowledge of the subject matter but also the ability to arrange thoughts and communicate them coherently to an audience. Although, writing is a bit difficult, it can be enhanced and developed through a wide series of experiences and trainings. Given the fact that the use of grammar assistant could also aid.

The primary objective of this research is to critically evaluate the effectiveness of virtual grammar assistants in improving writing skills. To achieve this goal, the researchers conducted a comprehensive review of existing literature on the topic, examining both the theoretical underpinnings and practical applications of these tools. Additionally, the researchers designed and executed empirical studies, gathering data to assess the impact of virtual grammar assistants on various aspects of writing, including grammar, syntax, and overall writing quality. This paper aims to explore and evaluate the effectiveness of virtual grammar assistants in enhancing writing skills, shedding light on their potential to revolutionize the way we approach written communication.

Impact of Virtual Grammar Assistant

In the present era, where technology has revolutionized every aspect of our lives, there are several remarkable resources that have emerged. Among these, one stands out as an invaluable tool for individuals facing challenges in writing English the virtual grammar assistant. This innovative digital tool has been specifically designed to address the needs of those who struggle with the intricacies of English grammar. The virtual grammar assistant operates by generating grammatically correct sentences based on the user's chosen topic. By harnessing the power of sophisticated algorithms, this tool analyzes the input and produces meticulously constructed sentences, empowering users to enhance their writing skills and overcome any obstacles they may encounter in expressing themselves in English for the knowledgeable audience seeking to refine their linguistic proficiency, this virtual grammar assistant serves as an indispensable aid it offers a seamless solution that enables users to elevate their command over the English language whether it is for academic, professional, or personal purposes, the usage of this tool guarantees accurate and effective communication (Xue et al., 2021).

As per Elbashir et al. (2022), in today's fast-paced and technology-driven world, students are constantly seeking ways to enhance their academic performance one crucial aspect of their education is improving their writing skills, especially when it comes to adhering to proper English grammar rules this is where virtual grammar assistants come into play, offering students a valuable tool to elevate their writing prowess using virtual grammar assistants can be a game-changer, particularly for students who aspire to excel in their academic endeavors These intelligent tools serve as reliable companions, walking alongside students throughout their writing journey. By harnessing the power of artificial intelligence, these assistants analyze and provide real-time feedback on grammar usage, sentence construction, and paragraph coherence. By conducting research on the impact of virtual grammar AI tools on students, it has been observed that their writing skills have seen a significant improvement as a result of utilizing these virtual assistants. Virtual grammar assistants have emerged as a valuable tool to enhance students' skills and precision in written communication, proving beneficial in their journey toward proficiency as stated by Awalin et al (2023), virtual grammar has become a valuable educational resource for those seeking to enhance their proficiency in English language and grammar, particularly in the era of internet and mobile advancements.

Research Questions

The general purpose of this study is to determine the effectiveness of Virtual Grammar Assistants in developing the writing skills of the students. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the effect of virtual grammar assistance to the student?
2. How can virtual grammar assistants help the students with their writing skills?
3. How may the use of a virtual grammar assistant be described?
4. What are the potential problems and ethical concerns while using virtual grammar assistants in education and language learning?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative approach to investigate the impact of virtual grammar assistance tools. By quantifying improvements in writing skills such as grammar, syntax, and overall composition, the research aims to provide statistically significant evidence of the effectiveness of virtual grammar assistance tools specifically Grammarly. Additionally, demographic variables and usage patterns will be analysed to identify any correlations or trends that may further enhance our understanding of how these tools impact different subgroups. Descriptive research design seeks to provide objective and measurable insights into the role of virtual grammar assistance in enhancing writing skills, offering valuable data for educators and writers alike. In terms of the respondents of this study, the researchers selected from a higher educational institution residing in Pampanga Philippines applicable to all Senior High School students from Grade 11 to

Grade 12 as their respondents. The respondents who join the study are those who can determine the effectiveness of a virtual grammar assistant on improving their writing skills. As well as those who can share their experience using it. Respondents are eligible to have knowledge and experience. The data needed for the study are gathered by the researchers via survey questions. In order for the respondents to respond, the researchers created a survey questionnaire based on the research questions. The survey questionnaire is used to gather demographic data as well as opinions and experiences relating to the research topic. Survey questionnaire is answerable with four option likert scale. In order to ensure survey respondents, the researchers make sure that the survey questions are clear and fair.

In this study, the sampling method known as purposive sampling is employed to refer to the deliberate selection of your respondents. As for Campbell et al. (2020), purposive sampling refers to the selection of participants with particular traits and data to address the study question, aim, and objectives throughout an investigation. The respondents are carefully selected in accordance with the needs of the study. The researchers float the instrument to the study's respondents during the data gathering phase. In addition, researchers conduct or discuss the instructions and to make sure that all the respondents will answer and are knowledgeable in Determining the effectiveness of Virtual Grammar Assistant on improving writing skills. This assessment will have 40 respondents, the researcher will make sure that all the respondents are not forced to answer the tool that we distributed to them. The respondents will have a chance to answer the survey questionnaire of their choice, in determining the respondents we make 20-item survey questions, the researcher will give the respondents enough time for them to answer the questions and analyze their answers. The respondents responses are analyzed using statistical tools included in descriptive statistics. According to Hayes et.al (2023), to find the mean, or average, sum up all the figures in the data set, then divide the total number of figures by the total number of figures in the collection. The information gathered was tabulated and processed manually and with a computer to determine the precise interpretation of the result. data were collected, tabulated, and analyzed. Those who often employ virtual grammar assistance to better their writing work are identified using descriptive statistics to observe the subject if there is a significant change when they used (virtual grammar assistant) and based on their demographic characteristics (sex, age, race, education), for which categorical variables the researchers applied a descriptive statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile

Sex

The respondents sex under their demographic profile: 16 of them are male and 24 of them are female. The majority of respondents are female, with 60 percent over the whole percentage, while the male respondents are 40 percent over 100 percent. 60 percent females and 40 percent male are equivalent to 100 percent.

Age

The age range is 16 years old, 17 years old, 18 years old, and 19 years old and older. 37.5 percent of the whole population is under 16 years old, which consists of 15 respondents, while half of the population, or 50 percent of 100, is under 17 years old, which consists of 20 respondents. On the other side, 5 percent of the population is 18 years old, which consists of 2 respondents, and the remaining 7.5 percent is 19 years old and older, which consists of 3 respondents. The majority of the respondents are 17 years old, the sum of all the percentages is equal to 100 percent.

Grade/Year Level

The grade or year level of the respondents involved in this study are senior high school grade 11 and grade 12 students. The 20 respondents out of 40 are grade 11 students, which is 50 percent of the population, while the other 20 respondents are grade 12 students, which is also half of 100 percent. The respondents grade or year level is equally divided, which is 100 percent in the general population.

Academic Strand

The respondents academic strands are Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM), General Academic Strand (GAS), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), and Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM). The 25 percent, or 10 respondents, are under the ABM Strand; the same is true for the GAS, which also has 25 percent and 10 respondents. The students in the HUMSS strand have 25 percent, or 10 respondents, as well. On the other side, the STEM strand also has 25 percent, or 10 respondents. The respondents' strands are equally divided, which sums up to 100 percent in total.

Table 1. Frequency Distribution and Percentage of the Respondents table

<i>Demographic Profile</i>		Frequency	%
Sex			
	Male	16	40
	Female	24	60
Age			
	16 y/o	15	37.5
	17 y/o	20	50
	18 y/o	2	5
	19 y/o and above	3	7.5
Grade/Year Level			
	11	20	50
	12	20	50
Academic Strand			
	ABM	10	25
	GAS	10	25
	HUMSS	10	25
	STEM	10	25

The Effectiveness of Virtual Grammar Assistant

Effect of virtual grammar assistance to the students

As per Fitria (2021), one of the hugely popular apps is Grammarly, however using this app has advantages and disadvantages. According to the data that the researchers gathered, an average of 2.02 disagreed that the virtual grammar assistant can improve writing skill, which means it has the lowest mean of all and can't really improve an individual writing skill. While an average of 3.30 strongly agreed that it helps to develop a written output. Respondents strongly agreed with an average of 3.42 that virtual grammar assistance has a good effect on academics, this shows that virtual grammar assistant has a good effect as this has the highest mean. Also, respondents agreed (3.05) this can enhance students' overall academic performances. The average of 3.18 agreed that virtual grammar assistance has a positive impact on students' confidence in their writing ability. The weighted mean is 2.99 agreed that virtual grammar assistants influence the students.

Virtual grammar assistance helps the student with their writing skills.

According to the AIContentfy (2023), with the article entitled "Revolutionizing Your Writing Process with AI Tools", they may aid with proofreading and editing, provide ideas for better word choices, strengthen sentence structure, and make suggestions for expanding vocabulary. In the data gathered by the researchers, an average of 3.35 strongly agreed that a virtual grammar assistant is helpful, this is totally strong as this has the highest mean and that concludes that these tools are helpful. Also, an average of 3.31 strongly agreed students think that there are differences between using these tools and their natural writing skills. With that, an average of 2.95 users agreed in favor of using this in their written outputs, this has the lowest meaning shows that users are not really in favor of using this. In addition, 3.22 on average agreed that these tools help the students

with their writing. An average of 3.05 agreed that presence of virtual grammar assistance offers substantial support to students striving to enhance their writing skills. The weighted mean 3.17, agreed that virtual grammar assistants help the students with their writing skills.

Use of virtual grammar assistant be described.

According to the AIContentfy (2023) with the article entitled “Discover the Benefits of using an Online Writing Assistant, you may drastically cut down on faults and blunders in your writing by using an online writing aid. With the average of 2.72, respondents agreed that virtual grammar assistants are usually needed by the students. With that, an average of 2.97 agreed that this is essential to the students. But with an average of 1.92, respondents disagreed that the virtual grammar assistant is only applicable to the students, respondents think that virtual grammar assistant also has a potential for others. 3.05 on an average, users of virtual grammar assistants agreed with its ability to enhance and proofreading capabilities, this has the highest mean, means that these tools have an ability to enhance and proofreading. With an average of 2.87, respondents agreed that the potential of virtual grammar assistants to reduce grammatical errors in documents strongly disagrees with the traditional proofreading methods. The weighted mean is 2.70, it shows that the use of virtual grammar assistant can be described.

Potential problems and ethical concerns while using virtual grammar assistants in education and language learning.

According to Teng & Yuen (2023), students can apparently complete a task with very little effort, which puts their capacity to develop critical thinking abilities at risk since it "leaves no room for the student to interpret and understand. Respondents agreed that virtual grammar assistance causes problems, with an average of 2.75. With an average of 2.62, respondents agreed that using these tools in education raises significant potential problems and ethical concern, these tools really don't raise potential problems as some of the respondents are the only ones who agreed. 2.92 of an average, reveal that respondents agreed that integrating grammar assistants in education and language learning raises concerns about over reliance on technology, potentially hindering students' independent language skills development, most of the respondents agreed that these tools raise concerns, with that, this has the highest mean. Also, with an average of 2.73, the respondents agreed that virtual grammar assistance in education introduces potential ethical issues related to data privacy and the collection of student writing samples for analysis. Respondents agreed that virtual grammar assistants in language learning create a risk of devaluing human educators' roles potentially leading to decrease in the quality of language instruction, an average of 2.62, this discusses that virtual grammar assistants didn't really create risk of devaluing human educators. The weighted mean is 2.72 and disclose that the respondents agreed that the virtual grammar assistance has potential problems and ethical concerns while using it in education and language learning.

The grand weighted mean is 2.89, a portion of the forty respondents concurred that using the online grammar checker helps with writing abilities improvement.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Effect of Virtual Grammar Assistance	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Effect of Virtual Grammar Assistant to the Students.			
1. Virtual Grammar Assistance can improve writing skills.	2.02	0.68	Disagree
2. Virtual Grammar Assistance help to assist to develop a written output.	3.30	0.64	Strongly Agree
3. Virtual Grammar Assistance has a good effect on academics.	3.42	0.54	Strongly Agree
4. Virtual Grammar Assistance enhances students' overall academic performances.	3.05	0.67	Agree
5. Virtual Grammar Assistance has a positive impact on students' confidence in their writing ability.	3.18	0.59	Agree
Weighted mean	2.99	0.62	Agree
Virtual Grammar Assistance helps the student with their writing skills.			
1. Virtual Grammar Assistance is helpful.	3.35	0.69	Strongly Agree
2. Students' think there's a difference between using virtual grammar assistance and their natural writing skills.	3.31	0.66	Strongly Agree
3. Users of virtual grammar assistance favor using this for their written output.	2.95	0.63	Agree
4. Virtual grammar assistance helps the students with their writing.	3.22	0.79	Agree
5. Presence of virtual grammar assistance offers substantial support to students striving to enhance their writing skills.	3.05	0.70	Agree
Weighted mean	3.17	0.69	Agree
Use of virtual grammar assistant be described.			
1. Students usually need to use a virtual grammar assistant.	2.72	0.77	Agree
2. Virtual Grammar Assistant is essential to students.	2.97	0.61	Agree
3. Virtual Grammar Assistant is only applicable to the students.	1.92	0.78	Disagree
4. Users of virtual grammar assistance agree with the ability to enhance proofreading capabilities.	3.05	0.55	Agree
5. Potential of virtual grammar assistant to reduce grammatical errors in documents strongly disagree with the traditional proof reading methods.	2.87	0.67	Agree
Weighted mean	2.70	0.67	Agree
Potential problems and ethical concerns while using virtual grammar assistants in education and language skills.			
1. Virtual Grammar Assistance causes problems.	2.75	0.76	Agree
2. Use of virtual grammar assistance in education raises significant potential problems and ethical concerns.	2.62	0.73	Agree
3. Integrating grammar assistants in education and language learning raises concerns about over reliance on technology potentially hindering students' in dependent language skills development.	2.92	0.72	Agree
4. Virtual Grammar Assistance in education introduces potential ethical issues related to data privacy and the collection of student writing samples for analysis.	2.73	0.76	Agree
5. Virtual Grammar Assistant in language learning creates a risk of devaluing human educators roles potentially leading to decrease in the quality of language instruction.	2.62	0.88	Agree
Weighted mean	2.72	0.77	Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	2.89	0.68	Agree

Conclusions

The following are the conclusions driven from the summary of the results.

1. Most of the respondents are female, consisting of 60 percent, while 40 percent are male. 20 respondents are 17 years old, which constitutes half of the total population, while the remaining 50 percent are under 16 years old, 18 years old, and 19 years old and older. The grade or year level of the respondents is between grade 11 and grade 12, which are equally divided. The academic strands of the

respondents are ABM, GAS, HUMSS, and STEM, which are also distributed fairly, with 25 percent per academic strand, for a total of 100 percent.

2. The respondents disagreed on the virtual grammar assistant's impact on writing skills (average 2.02) but strongly agreed on its effectiveness in developing written output (3.30). It also received strong affirmation for positively impacting academics (3.42) and enhancing overall academic performance (3.05). Agreement (3.18) was noted for its positive influence on students' confidence. The weighted mean of 2.99 indicates an overall agreement on the effect of virtual grammar assistants on students.
 3. The respondents strongly agreed on its helpfulness (3.35 on average) and expressed a strong consensus (3.31 on average) about differences from natural writing skills. Users, on average (2.95), favored incorporating virtual grammar assistance in their written outputs. Respondents, on average (3.22), agreed that these tools effectively support students in writing, with an additional agreement (3.05 on average) that the presence of virtual grammar assistance substantially aids students in enhancing their writing skills. The weighted mean of 3.17 emphasizes the overall agreement that virtual grammar assistants significantly contribute to improving students' writing skills.
 4. The results show that respondents generally agree on the importance of virtual grammar assistants, particularly for students (average rating 2.72). They emphasize the significance of these tools to students, receiving an average rating of 2.97. However, there is disagreement about the exclusivity of virtual grammar assistants to students, with an average rating of 1.92. Users agree (average rating 3.05) that these tools enhance proofreading capabilities. Respondents (average rating 2.87) recognize the potential of virtual grammar assistants to surpass traditional proofreading methods in reducing grammatical errors. The overall weighted mean of 2.70 indicates a positive view of using virtual grammar assistants.
 5. Respondents' express agreement on problems, with an average rating of 2.75, and highlight significant concerns (avg. rating 2.62) in education. They also note worries about over-reliance on technology (avg. rating 2.92) and potential ethical issues related to data privacy (avg. rating 2.73). The risk of devaluing human educators' roles in language learning is acknowledged (avg. rating 2.62). The weighted mean of 2.72 reflects respondents' overall agreement on the challenges and ethical considerations of using virtual grammar assistance. The grand weighted mean is 2.89.
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Recommendations

In consideration of the results, and conclusion, the following recommendations are suggested:

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1. The virtual grammar assistant serves as a valuable tool for students, fostering confidence, motivation, and improved writing skills by identifying and correcting grammatical errors. It directs their focus on specific areas for grammar enhancement, contributing to overall writing growth.
2. Teachers benefit from online grammar assistance as it efficiently addresses basic errors, saving time on corrections. These tools provide immediate feedback, offer examples for language and punctuation, and enhance the quality of teaching materials. Integrating virtual grammar support simplifies instruction and nurtures students' independence in editing their own writing.
3. For school administrators, this study offers a basis to integrate virtual grammar assistants for composing professional communications. Clear and professional grammar in emails, announcements, and reports is crucial for interpreting and enforcing school policies, rules, and regulations.
4. Curriculum planners find value in the study results, as virtual grammar assistants contribute to improving grammar and writing skills. This enhancement can be passed on to educators and students, elevating the level of professionalism in papers and positively impacting the institution's reputation.
5. The study provides a foundation for future researchers, offering insights into the effectiveness of virtual grammar assistants. It serves as a reference point for further studies, fostering knowledge development in this specific area. Future researchers can build upon these findings to advance their understanding and share insights with subsequent studies.
6. The study can recommend it to future researchers. Future researchers can compare two different apps or websites, and these are Grammarly and Quill Bot. This comparison can help users identify which is more reliable to use and more accurate and helpful.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research strictly adheres to the ethical standards set by the institution and the body of knowledge. All information and data coming from the respondents are solely for academic purposes only. In line also with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researchers strictly preserved the anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents.

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